

120 years of untangling the divaricate habit: a review

Supplementary Material

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Supplementary Material 1: List of complementary readings about divaricate species. These scientific publications were not cited in the body of the review because they do not bring more significant elements about the evolution or the development of the divaricates than the studies already cited. However, we aim to offer a list of the scientific publications relating to the divaricates that is as exhaustive as possible, because these readings might provide ideas of future research to the reader. We do not include floras and other descriptive work that only list divaricate species.

- Christian (2003): review of the climatic and moa-browsing hypotheses, and advertises ongoing research on the photoprotection hypothesis.
- Fadzly & Burns (2010): study crypsis of both the juvenile divaricate juvenile and the non-divaricate adult forms of *Elaeocarpus hookerianus* Raoul.
- Forsyth et al. (2010): study the impact of introduced deer on the ecosystems of New Zealand, showing that divaricates are part of deer diet. Also review the evidence about moa diet, comparing it to their results for deer.
- Gamage & Jesson (2007) and Gamage (2011): compare shade tolerance of four congeneric pairs of homoblastic and heteroblastic species. Among the heteroblastic species, one is a heteroblastic divaricate species with a quasi-divaricate juvenile, two are divaricate species that are heteroblastic by their leaf shape, not architecture, and the last one is non-divaricate its whole life. All the homoblastic species are non-divaricate. They showed that the juvenile forms do not seem to be an adaptation to shaded environments, but it is difficult to isolate the effect of the divaricate habit itself from their statistical results because they tested homoblastic versus heteroblastic, not non-divaricate versus divaricate.
- Lee & Johnson (1984): compare the nutrient content of divaricate and non-divaricate *Coprosma* species. They show significant differences but argue that their experiment cannot tell us about the potential importance of these differences in regards to herbivory.
- Pole & Moore (2011): report fossil leaves that have similar shape and size to those of extant *Myrsine divaricata* A.Cunn. from a deposit dated 6-6.5 Myo (late Miocene), but because no branching architecture was preserved it cannot be reliably inferred that this species (*Myrsine waihiensis* sp. nov.) was similarly divaricate.
- Turnbull et al. (2002): reply to the criticism of Lusk (2002) on the conclusions of Howell

et al. (2002).

- Whitaker (1987), Lord & Marshall (2001) and Wotton et al. (2016): develop the idea that native lizards (geckos and skinks) are seeds dispersers for divaricate species. Lord & Marshall (2001) formulated the hypothesis that the cage architecture, once it appeared, provided a diurnal refuge for lizards, which would consume the fruits hidden in the cage and subsequently disperse the seeds. Lord & Marshall (2001) and Wotton et al. (2016) suggested that seed dispersal by lizards may have favoured the selection of white/blue/pale fruits in divaricates.
- Wilson (1991): distribution maps of some New Zealand divaricate and heteroblastic divaricate species in Canterbury and Westland.

Supplementary Figure 1: Example of an abrupt shift from a divaricate juvenile form to a non-divaricate adult form in a metamorphic heteroblastic divaricate species, *Pennantia corymbosa* J.R.Forst. & G.Forst. (Pennantiaceae; Halswell Quarry Park, Christchurch, Canterbury, New Zealand). In this photo, the shift happens around 1.80 m high (photo: KJLM, September 2014).

Supplementary Figure 2: African boxthorn (*Lycium ferocissimum* Miers; Solanaceae), growing on a low cliff in Stoddart Point Recreation Reserve (Diamond Harbour, Canterbury, New Zealand). A species with interlaced wide-angle branching closely resembling some New Zealand divaricates, except for very stiff spines and relatively large leaves (photo: KJLM, November 2017).

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